

Ways to Organize and Improve the Market of Household Services

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Abstract: This article considers the issue of modern trends in the placement of household service enterprises in modern conditions. The analysis shows that the principles of the development of the network of household service enterprises in the areas of new buildings have changed, as well as the need to improve approaches to the planning of retail and household infrastructure of residential areas. According to the results of the survey, the author studied the factors affecting the behavior of consumers of individual services.

Keywords: personal services, location of enterprises, questionnaire survey, planning of personal services enterprises

Introduction. At the moment, large-scale reforms are being implemented in the field of housing construction in Uzbekistan. This, first of all, affects the appearance of cities. In recent years, there has been a shift from low-rise construction to high-rise buildings and high-rise buildings. In every major city, the creation of a so-called "city" with buildings of 12-16 stories and higher will lead to changes in the utility, transportation and social infrastructure. In addition, multi-storey houses are being built in rural settlements.

The result of changes in the urban planning policy is a significant change in the sphere of trade and household services for the population. The high population density and the increase in living comfort have created strict requirements for the organization of household services. More and more new types of consumer preferences for individual services are being formed. For example, it is becoming common to have goods and services delivered directly to your home. Digital technologies are increasingly evolving to provide personalized services.

In such conditions, the improvement of the methodology of placement of retail trade and household service enterprises becomes an important problem. Modern trends in the development of the service sector in settlements indicate the need to abandon the traditional regulatory method of locating household service enterprises. First, the previous classification of individual and household services has long been outdated due to fundamental changes in the living conditions of the population. Second, the need for individual services varies greatly not only across districts but also within a single subdistrict.

Until now, the main indicator of the development of the service sector, in particular, of household service enterprises, is the provision of the population with the number of seats or other capacity indicators (the number of places in hairdressing salons, the number of visits). household service enterprises, the number of workshops per 1000 inhabitants, etc.). The development experience of countries shows that the high quality of the service sector does not directly depend on the standard density of the network of service enterprises.

Analysis of used literature. The development of the household service system and its effectiveness has been the object of research by many scientists. Goncharov AA in his study proposes a management system concept for the development and support of household services

to the population. This system should ensure the effectiveness of the development of the network of household service enterprises through local government bodies. Shadskaya IG, while studying the trends in the development of the household services market in rural areas, identifies dynamically developing market segments that have development potential and are in the stage of decline. The author suggests the organization of marketing research by the city government, as well as the development of a program for the development of the household services market at the regional level, in particular, the regulation and information provision of this market. In the case of Mairova A.Yu. Based on a detailed analysis of the structure of the household services market, it is proposed to improve the management system by establishing city departments of household services. Some authors pay attention to the development of management of enterprises in the field of household services within the framework of optimization of their number and density. There are also developments based on the development of the household services market as a mechanism for regulating the provision of individual services. The analysis of the conducted research allowed us to conclude that in the development of the household services market, it is necessary to plan the placement of a network of enterprises in this field.

It is necessary to pay respect to the scientists who made a great contribution to the development of the theory of marketing in the economy, and the researches conducted in the field of economics in our country for many years were conducted on the basis of national characteristics. M. Muhammedov, M. Paradaev, R. Ibrohimov are among them. Abdullaev Yu., Saliev A., Sharifkhojaev M., Khodiev B., Rahimova D., Ergashkhojaeva Sh., Sh Musaeva and others.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, sampling and observation methods were used in the research process.

Based on this concept, the formation of a network of household service enterprises in the regions is carried out according to the principle of sufficiency, that is, there should be as many enterprises as are needed for a certain part of the population. This approach is accepted not only by local government bodies, but also by entrepreneurs themselves. Local authorities use this approach in allocating land for the creation of business structures. For example, if there is already a shoe repair shop in the area, a new one is considered inappropriate. At the same time, the entrepreneurs themselves, only psychologically, do not want to enter into competition with the existing enterprise.

Such an approach leads to the fact that domestic service providers have almost no competitors in the local market. Most importantly, with this approach, there is an exodus of customers from this local market.

At the same time, the experience of developing beauty salons (bridal service salons) in the cities and villages of Uzbekistan shows that increased competition and the concentration of several enterprises in a small geographical area will help to increase the flow of customers and maintain everyone's income. . entrepreneurs. We observe a similar effect for other types of consumer service businesses as well as retail businesses. The location of several similar retail outlets in the vicinity does not lead to a decrease in the number of customers, on the contrary, it leads to their increase. This trend is also observed in the development of a network of pharmacies, diagnostic centers, "chicken houses", real estate agencies, etc. We believe that this situation is related to the change in consumer behavior of the population.

The problem of studying the market of household services in the Republic of Uzbekistan is related to the lack of a system of statistical monitoring of its condition. Public service enterprises appear in two sections of the statistical report: services and small business and entrepreneurship status. However, the analysis of statistical reports shows that household services are not directly reflected in them. In the Services report, personal services appear under individual services, other services, and retail services. In the reporting section for small businesses, there is no clear picture for consumer service businesses either. In addition, the household services market has hardly been studied in analytical studies in recent years. Based on this, in our research, we focused on studying the situation of individual services.

Observations show that a high concentration of individual and small enterprises is characteristic of the sector of individual service to the population, that is, all of the above economic entities are related to direct contact with the customer in one way or another. As the main concept for studying this problem, we used one of the effective methods of marketing research - the questionnaire survey method. This method attracts attention due to its simplicity, low time consumption and coverage of various categories of consumers.

Analysis and results. A survey was conducted among potential consumers of individual services. Our research conducted in several districts and rural settlements of the city of Samarkand showed the following characteristics of the wishes of consumers in the provision of individual services. The study deals with the study of the factors influencing the choice of a particular retail and consumer service enterprise. Respondents were residents of the area who agreed to answer several questions in the survey. The questionnaire consisted of the following questions:

1. Enjoy the convenient location of area retail and convenience stores.
2. How to get to retail and service businesses?
3. What most influences the choice of certain retail and consumer service businesses?
4. Which location of home service businesses do you find most appealing?

As a preliminary basis, we considered this research as exploratory, so the responses of the respondents were also considered preliminary. In addition, the survey conditions and anonymity do not allow the results of this survey to be used as a basis for serious scientific conclusions.

At the same time, we consider the answers of the respondents worthy of attention. The overwhelming majority of respondents gave a positive answer to the first question, that is, they are satisfied with the state of trade and household infrastructure in their place of residence.

For the second question, about 50% of respondents indicated that they visit several establishments at the same time, more than 35% made a traditional visit to selected outlets on their way home, and only 12% indicated that they visited a specific facility.

The third question of the questionnaire allowed the respondents to express their opinions, so it was not possible to choose one priority factor. The most common answers are: loyalty to one seller, attractive prices, the range offered, choice, honesty of the seller, good service.

Respondents were interested in the question of the structure of household service enterprises, that is, the uneven density of their locations. The answers to the fourth question were placed in the following sequence: near the place of residence - 44%, the possibility of parking a car - 38%, on the way to work - 12%, no clear choice - 6%. It should be noted that the respondents have a positive attitude to the presence of several similar service enterprises at the same time.

Based on our research, we have systematized the main reasons for evaluating household infrastructure enterprises from consumers. These include: the freedom to choose the subject of providing household services, that is, there should be as many of these enterprises as possible; ensure the availability of household services, that is, their location and working hours should be unlimited; variety of offered services, i.e. consideration of individual needs when offering and providing individual services; quality of service, i.e. completeness and speed of service.

The conducted research allowed us to formulate the concept of development of the household services market, the main rule of which is to create conditions for the free formation of supply in the market of household services. In the implementation of the proposed concept, special attention is paid to the deregulation of the number of household service enterprises, as well as to the stimulation of their growth through self-employment programs of the population.

Summary. Based on the conducted theoretical and practical research, we propose to develop new approaches to the development of the household services market, based on the stimulation of competition in this field. It is necessary to create a household service environment containing an

unlimited number of household service entities. In addition, it is proposed to move from the distributed nature of the placement of enterprises to the nodal principle, that is, the concentration of several similar household service enterprises in a limited area, which will encourage the use of these services.

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